

**Deliverable D-JRP-
PARADISE-WP4.2**
**Report on the selection of
highly affine nanobodies
specific for *C. parvum* and
*G. duodenalis***

**Workpackage 4 of
JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE**

Responsible Partners: P27-ISS, P11-
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D-JRP-PARADISE-WP4.2

REPORT ON THE SELECTION OF HIGHLY AFFINE NANOBODIES SPECIFIC FOR *C. PARVUM* AND *G. DUODENALIS*

BACKGROUND

This is a public deliverable of One Health EJP Joint Research Project:

JRP19-ET1.1-PARADISE – *PARAsite Detection, ISolation and Evaluation*

(<https://onehealthjep.eu/jrp-paradise/>);

Work Package:

JRP- PARADISE –WP4 Parasite enrichment strategies;

Task:

JRP-PARADISE-PARADISE-WP4-T1 Development of pre-DNA extraction enrichment strategies.

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PARADISE WP4 aims to improve the performance of current approaches to detect *Cryptosporidium* and *Giardia* (oo)cyst contamination in food through the development of parasite enrichment strategies, which should improve the sensitivity of detection and deliver less expensive methods applicable to food matrices.

Objectives of PARADISE WP4 are:

- ✓ To develop two pre-DNA extraction protocols based on two alternative affinity reagents, nanobodies (single-chain variable fragment antibodies) and aptamers (oligonucleotides that bind to a specific target molecule);
- ✓ To assess nanobodies and aptamers application for magnetic capture of *C. parvum* and *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts in different matrices;
- ✓ To develop a protocol for post-DNA enrichment to concentrate parasite DNA based on hybridization of target-specific biotinylated probes.
- ✓ To evaluate pre- and post-DNA extraction enrichment strategies by inter-laboratory comparison

This deliverable reports on the first objective of PARADISE WP4, i.e., the screening and selection of highly affine and specific nanobodies with the ability of binding *C. parvum* or *G. duodenalis* (oo)cysts.

Nanobodies represent the variable domain (VHH, antigen binding domain) of heavy chain antibodies that are part of the humoral immune system of camelids. These small peptides (approximately 15 kDa) are able to bind target antigens with affinities and specificities similar to conventional antibodies. They are also structurally more stable and often resist harsh conditions such as high temperature treatment. The VHH domains are easily expressed in *E. coli* and can be purified by standard affinity chromatography in high amounts, which significantly reduces production cost. Given the low number of available antibodies and tools for immunodetection and purification of *G. duodenalis* cysts and *C. parvum* oocysts, the aim of this work was to screen and select for highly affine and specific nanobodies against these targets.

Towards this aim, crude antigen preparations of whole *G. duodenalis* and *C. parvum* (oo)cysts were prepared and shipped to an external contractor for immunization of two individual alpacas using a standard immunization scheme. Lymphocytes of whole blood of immunized animals were prepared and used for RNA preparation. Subsequently, cDNA libraries were generated encoding for VHH domains ("nanobodies") from each immunized animal. The libraries were enriched for binders of (oo)cysts antigens either by using crude antigens and/or structurally intact (oo)cysts. Potential binders were further screened for binding to (oo)cysts by an immunofluorescence assay. The general workflow of this activity is depicted in Figure 1.

Results of these screening assays revealed 10 potential binders (VHHs) reacting to *G. duodenalis* cysts in the immunofluorescence assay. These nanobodies are currently being expressed and purified by affinity chromatography for further testing.

So far, for *C. parvum*, none of the enriched nanobodies was confirmed by immunofluorescence analysis to recognize oocysts. For the latter, further screening assays are currently being performed using modified approaches, i.e. to enrich nanobodies using structurally intact oocysts.

Figure 1: General workflow to identify specific VHH domains (nanobodies) against *G. duodenalis* cysts or *C. parvum* oocysts.

In conclusion, all steps towards identification and selection of VHH domains (nanobodies) directed against *G. duodenalis* cysts and *C. parvum* oocysts have been successfully performed. Several VHH domains that potentially bind *G. duodenalis* cysts have been identified and are undergoing further characterization using ELISA, flow cytometry and Biacore analysis. Depending on affinity, the selected nanobodies will be engineered to produce bivalent nanobodies and/or used to coat magnetic beads. A workflow for enrichment of *G. duodenalis* cyst from food matrices will be designed accordingly. Further modified screening approaches are necessary to identify nanobodies against *C. parvum* oocysts.